

ISic3403

Fragment of a monumental Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

Not yet located

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based upon Orsi's notebook

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ortygia, extracted from the wall bordering the last canal/ditch linking the great and small harbours, on the corner looking towards the great harbout , in late 1888, at which point noted and recorded by Orsi, and transfered to the museum 4 December 1888

Coordinates

37.0626632,15.288339

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 12254

Physical Description

A large block of compact limestone ('calcare di Canicattini')

Dimensions

Height 36 cm

Width 70 cm

Depth 90 cm

Layout

A single line of monumental letters across the broad face of the block

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Elegant deep (14mm), v-cut letters of regular form. Kappa with short equal arms; sigma with horizontal top and bottom strokes; alpha with straight bar.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 210 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. [---]ΣKATA[---]

Apparatus

Text of Orsi, Taccuino 2.74

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644948

PHI 140309

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0015b (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 371
Orsi, Paolo 2018. I Taccuini. I. Riproduzione anastatica e trascrizione dei Taccuini 1-4. *Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Monumenti Antichi. Serie Miscellanea.* Rome. At Tacc. 2, p. 74

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3403. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358486>